

Speculation on $[p, x] = -i\hbar$ From the Point of View of Information

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 23, 2025

$[P, X] = -i\hbar$ (where $P = -i\hbar d/dx$ and X is the position operator) is a well-known relation from quantum mechanics and is often said to represent differences in the order of measuring p and x . In (1), this relation is linked with electromagnetic fields and linear response theory. Here, we try to consider a free quantum particle $\exp(ipx)$. If such a particle is not interacting, then it should be largely classical, i.e. have a classical momentum p and move as $x=vt$. It, however, is not entirely classical even if it is not interacting with 2-slit type apparati because $\exp(ipx)$ is a special probability which tracks motion in space. In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ tracks its phase which may be different from the phase of another particle leading to interference at a target. Thus, quantum effects are occurring in terms of information¹. We use the term information¹ to distinguish between information from information theory ($\ln(\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L})$). We next note that applying an operator X does not mean finding a single x_0 point, but rather a distribution $x \exp(ipx)$. We argue that this product is now two pieces of x information throughout space. The P operator $-i\hbar d/dx$ seems to be linked to information in space because it usually acts on $\exp(ipx)$ which is already based on a known p value. Furthermore, it is p which defines $\hbar/p = \Delta x$, the natural gradations in space. Thus, p is linked with spatial information and not vice versa. Thus, $X P \exp(ipx)$ has no effect on p , but the reverse $P X$ is not the same as P is linked with x information for any x , even x or any other x function. Thus, $-i\hbar d/dx$ seems to be an informational operator. Acting on $x \exp(ipx)$, it tries to find information about this product. We note that one takes the derivative d/dx in the neighbourhood of some x_0 , and for argument sake. one may choose this x_0 to be 0 such that x is part of the low x expansion of $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, x carries information linked to an $\exp(ix)$ and this leads to $[p, x] = i\hbar$.

$[P, X] = -i\hbar$

$[P, X] = i\hbar$ is a well-known relation in quantum mechanics and is often said to demonstrate the difference of first measuring x and the p (momentum) in a system versus first measuring p and then x . In (1), this relation is considered in terms of the electromagnetic field and linear response theory. Here, we wish to consider it in terms of a free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ because such a particle has a fixed, a priori known p value.

Free Quantum Particle

A free quantum particle is described by a wavefunction: $\exp(ipx) / \sqrt{L}$ ((1)), where L is an arbitrary length. The wavefunction shows that there is a natural length in the space given by:

$$\text{Wavelength} = \hbar/p \quad ((2))$$

One might argue, however, that if the particle is not interacting, then it has a p (which must be known a priori otherwise one cannot write $\exp(ipx)$ in the first place) and moves as $x=vt$. The fact that there is an \hbar/p length in space may seem like irrelevant information, but it seems it

is not. It seems that the free particle keeps track of its phase in $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, two particles with different phases may interfere at a target. Thus, we argue that in addition to describing the fact that the particle may interact with two slit separated by \hbar/p at the same time, $\exp(ipx)$ is tracking information. As a result, we further argue that:

$$P \text{ operator} = -i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} \quad ((3))$$

is associated with information1. Here we use the term information1 to indicate that we are not necessarily talking about information from information theory. The point we make is that for a free particle one knows p , so one does need a wavefunction and a P operator to obtain it. Without knowledge of p there is no wavefunction. Thus, P seems to be somehow linked with information1 present in any x function because p defines \hbar/p units in space.

The second point we make is that if one measures position with an X operator, one obtains a distribution, not a point, i.e.

$$x \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

We stress that both $\exp(ipx)$ and x represent information1 throughout space. One has a product of information1 and the P operator may act on both as it seems that this operator is trying to obtain a certain kind of information. In the case of $\exp(ipx)$, this information1 is p , the momentum. The question then becomes: What is the information for x ?

We argue that a derivative d/dx may be taken at any x point. In particular, one may focus on $x_0=0$. In this region, x is tiny and so:

$$\exp(-ix) = 1 - ix + \frac{1}{2}(ix)(ix) + \dots \quad ((4))$$

In such a case, $-i \frac{d}{dx} \exp(-ix) = -1$ ($\hbar=1$) which is the same as $-i \hbar \frac{d}{dx}$ acting on x . In other words, near $x_0=0$, ix is $1 - \exp(-ix)$, i.e. represents momentum information of 1.

As a result, one must be careful when considering the effects of the operator P because it seems to obtain information from any x function, even one linked with a distribution. For example, one may have:

$$f(x) \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

as a more general statement, and P seeks to find information1 about $f(x)$ even though $f(x)\exp(ipx)$ is a statistical distribution.

We suggest examining $[P,X] = -i \hbar$ using a free particle $\exp(ipx)$ because it is a much simpler scenario than a bound wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$, for which one really does not know p . For a free particle, one knows the value of p a priori and so $P = -i\hbar \frac{d}{dx}$ seems to be an operator which is trying to find 'p' related information because p is not only an momentum, but is linked to spacing in space \hbar/p .

We note that usually one sees p and x product terms in statistical (phase space) type classical functions which need to be converted into quantum mechanics.

P Contains Information About x Space and not Vice Versa

If one considers the free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, even though it appears symmetric in p and x , p is a number and x is a running variable. Thus, p carries information¹ about space, i.e. \hbar/p , and not vice versa. P acting on $x \exp(ipx)$ retrieves information about both space functions x and $\exp(ipx)$. X acting on $P \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ brings back no information about p .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to examine the quantum relationship $[P,X] = -i \hbar$ in terms of information¹ (here 1 indicates that we don't mean information from information theory). We use the free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, which is the simplest and is already based on a known p . One does not need a $P = -i\hbar d/dx$ operator find p . Nevertheless, its existence seems to be linked with information¹. $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle tracks information¹, namely phase in space which is linked to p because $\text{wavelength} = \hbar/p$. If one measures x first, then this it is not an x_0 point measure, but a distribution in space like $\exp(ipx)$ so $x \exp(ipx)$ is a product of information¹'s in space. We argue that $i x$ is like $1 - \exp(-ix)$ near $x=0$ and so x itself contains P information. This is why measuring P and then X differs from measuring X and the P because p contains information¹ about x space \hbar/p for both x and $\exp(ipx)$ while X is not linked with information about p .

References

1. Cetto A.M. and de la Pena, L. Origins of the Quantum Operator Formalism and its connection with Linear Response Theory April 7, 2025
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/reader/36a0e565ef09cb4b7cd5d7082868cb0d880f8d89>